

Supplemental File 1.

Supplemental Table 1. Breakfast diary.

Day	1
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Time of levothyroxine intake:

Time of breakfast:

Select the food items that were part of your breakfast:

<input type="checkbox"/> High-fiber products such as:	<u>Quantity:</u>
<input type="checkbox"/> Bread	
<input type="checkbox"/> Cereals	
<input type="checkbox"/> Coffee	<u>Quantity:</u>
<input type="checkbox"/> Dairy products such as milk, yogurt, or cheese	<u>Quantity:</u>
<input type="checkbox"/> Fruits and/or fruit juice	<u>Quantity:</u>
<input type="checkbox"/> Soy products	<u>Quantity:</u>

Patients were instructed to keep a daily breakfast diary during the entire study period.

Supplemental Table 2. Breakfast content 5-7 days per week.

	Fasting group (n=43)	Breakfast group (n=45)
Identical breakfast content, n (%)	30 (69.8)	29 (64.4)
Bread, n (%)	26 (60.5)	21 (46.7)
Cereals, n (%)	2 (4.7)	6 (13.3)
Coffee, n (%)	25 (58.1)	26 (57.8)
Dairy products, n (%)	23 (53.5)	23 (51.1)
Fruits and/or fruit juice, n (%)	4 (9.3)	4 (8.9)
Soy products, n (%)	0	2 (4.4)

Data presented as n (%).

Supplemental Table 3. Sensitivity analyses of TSH stability after exclusion of relevant subgroups.

Excluded subgroup	N	Fasting group (%)	Breakfast group (%)	P
Patients using soft-gel formulation (%)	7	71.1	72.1	NS
Patients receiving block-and-replace therapy	5	75.6	73.8	NS
Patients who did not have an LT4 dose adjustment due to continuing non-fasting ingestion or using soft-gel formulation, as well as patients whose dose was decreased after switching from non-fasting to fasting ingestion	12	73.0	71.8	NS

Data presented as % with p for difference between groups.

Supplemental Table 4. TSH stability and breakfast content.

Breakfast content 5-7 days per week	TSH stability		P
	Yes (%)	No (%)	
Identical breakfast content	66.2	69.6	NS
Bread	55.4	47.8	NS
Cereals	7.7	13.0	NS
Coffee	58.5	56.5	NS
Dairy products	49.2	60.9	NS
Fruits and/or fruit juice	10.8	4.3	NS
Soy products	3.1	0	NS

Data presented as % with p for difference between groups.

Supplemental Table 5. Mean changes in TSH, FT4 and TT3 levels.

Group	Ingestion	N	TSH (mIU/L)	FT4 (pmol/L)	TT3 (nmol/L)
Fasting vs. breakfast	Fasting	43	0.29 ± 1.02	-0.49 ± 2.36	0.06 ± 0.18
	Breakfast	45	0.27 ± 1.02	-1.00 ± 2.71	0.08 ± 0.23
Crossover	Fasting	18	0.21 ± 1.08	-0.88 ± 2.01	0.06 ± 0.15
	Breakfast	18	0.05 ± 1.42	1.03 ± 3.08	-0.01 ± 0.23

Data presented as mean ± standard deviation. TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; FT4, free thyroxine; TT3, total triiodothyronine.

Mean changes in TSH, FT4 and TT3 levels from baseline to study completion were comparable between the fasting and the breakfast group. Similar results were observed in the crossover group.

Supplemental Table 6. Levothyroxine dose adjustments.

Time point	Breakfast group (n=45)					Fasting group (n=43)				
	N in study	N without dose change	N with dose change (range in mcg)		Median dose change in mcg (range)	N in study	N without dose change	N with dose change (range in mcg)		Median dose change in mcg (range)
			Increase	Decrease				Increase	Decrease	
T6	45	24	13 (+12.0 to +25.0)	8 (-10.7 to -13.0)	0 (-13.0 to +25.0)	43	36	3 (+12.0 to +13.0)	4 (-12.5 to -13.0)	0 (-13.0 to +13.0)
T12	45	36	3 (+12.0 to +13.0)	6 (-12.5 to -14.3)	0 (-14.3 to +13.0)	43	42	0	1 (-13.0)	0 (-13.0 to 0)
T18	10	8	1 (+25.0)	1 (-25.0)	0 (-25.0 to +25.0)	7	6	0	1 (-12.5)	0 (-12.5 to 0)
T24	4	3	0	1 (-12.5)	0 (-12.5 to 0)	3	3	0	0	0 (0 to 0)

Mcg, microgram.

Dose adjustments are shown from T6 onward, as a per-protocol 15% dose increase had already been implemented in the breakfast group at T0.

Supplemental Table 7. Reasons for opting out of crossing over.

Reason	N
No experienced burden with fasting ingestion	11
Anxiety related to TSH dysregulation	5
Other medical treatment not related to thyroid disease	2
Time commitment	2
Personal circumstances	2
Levothyroxine treatment discontinued as part of block-and-replace therapy for Graves' Disease	1
Exclusion due to metastatic malignancy	1
Exclusion due to non-compliance	1

TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Supplemental Table 8. ThyPRO-39 scores.

Scales	Fasting (n=18)		Non-fasting (n=18)	
	Median (0-100)	IQR	Median (0-100)	IQR
Goiter symptoms *	2.0	2.0-15.0	2.0	2.0-2.0
Hyperthyroid symptom	13.0	8.0-20.5	13.0	2.0-23.0
Hypothyroid symptom	15.6	6.3-37.5	18.8	4.7-31.3
Eye symptoms	14.0	1.0-20.0	14.0	4.5-20.0
Tiredness	33.0	17.0-58.0	33.0	17.0-42.0
Cognitive problems	10.5	1.0-31.0	14.0	1.0-21.0
Anxiety	1.0	1.0-18.0	1.01	1.0-14.0
Depressive symptoms	10.5	7.0-29.0	7.0	7.0-25.5
Emotional Susceptibility	13.0	7.0-22.8	7.0	13.0-24.5
Impaired Social life	0	0-10.3	0	0-8.0
Impaired Daily life	0	0-15.0	0	0-18.5
Cosmetic Complaints	16.5	9.3-28.0	12.0	1.0-16.5
Overall QoL-impact	0	0-6.25.0	0	0-25.0
Composite score:	13.1	8.0-25.0	13.6	8.0-20.5

Data presented as median [interquartile range] *p < 0.05 vs. non-fasting ingestion. QoL, quality of life.

Patients were instructed to respond to the questionnaire based on their experiences over the past four weeks. The questionnaire included 13 QoL domains, each with 3-9 questions rated on a 0-4 Likert scale. Sum scores per QoL domain were transformed to a 0-100 scale. The 'composite' score was a calculation of the: tiredness, cognitive problems, anxiety, depressive symptoms, emotional susceptibility, impaired social life, impaired daily life and overall QoL-impact scales, as a way to represent the overall impact on QoL.